

THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

Umarova Feruza Nigmatovna

**Teacher, English Department, Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and
Agricultural Mechanization Engineers National Research University,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6625102>

Communicative competence is a multi-component complex socio-psychological concept. The essence of communicative competence is the ability to organize speech activities depending on the tasks and specific communicative situation based on the acquired knowledge and skills. The quality of the manifestation of competence in communicative activity we call communicative competence. The analysis of psychological-didactic literature showed that the problem of the formation of communicative competence is the most discussed. Various methodical schools are looking for ways to form communicative competence. The purpose of our study was to determine the pedagogical conditions that ensure the effective formation of communicative competence in teaching a foreign language. Competence in a foreign language is the goal and result of special education. The formation of communicative competence of students in teaching a foreign language is carried out through the development in the aggregate of communicative, language competences and linguistic-cultural competence, which is carried out through familiarization with material about the country of the language being studied.

In recent years, the problem of the formation of communicative skills of listening has increasingly attracted the attention of teachers, psychologists, psycholinguists and methodologists. A serious theoretical search is conducted in the study of this complex process. The formation of communicative listening skills is of great importance, since the mastery of a foreign language and the development of speech skills is carried out mainly through listening. Therefore, listening should be developed better than other skills, but putting on listening causes great difficulties.

For successful learning, listening requires a didactic and methodical system that takes into account these difficulties and provides for their overcoming. One of the effective conditions for the formation of communicative competence is the definition of a tool or tool, the use of which contributes to a qualitative change in the level of formation of communicative competence in a foreign language in high school students. A generally accepted means of generating knowledge and skills is exercise. Communicative competence is formed through various communication exercises aimed at overcoming communicative difficulties arising

in the process of learning a foreign language. Studying a variety of communicative exercises and the role of exercises in the learning process, V. L. Skalkin wrote: “most often, the goal in a lesson is not achieved precisely because there are no bad or good exercises, but there are teachers who either do well or wrongly are using. In other words, in the hands of the master of the exercise, “terrible power” .

The formation of communicative competence in teaching a foreign language, should be carried out on the basis of the use of a system of communicative exercises to overcome phonetic difficulties and difficulties in learning anticipation. Anticipation is anticipation or prediction. For listening skills, communication is anticipation of perceived information from a foreign language text to listen to. E.I. Passov believes that in the listening process there is a pre-tuning of the organs of speech, which contributes to the excitation of some models in the brain. Such pre-tuning is the basis for the functioning of the anticipation mechanism. This may be anticipation of the structural side of speech and its substantive side . The formation of communicative competence of students in learning a foreign language is a long and complex process. It involves the implementation of a competence-based approach aimed at the formation and improvement of not one type of communicative skills, but in the aggregate of all components of communicative competence: communicative skills of listening, reading, speaking and writing. Only then can we talk about the formation of a systemic set of competencies, mastering them in the complex. Thus, the effectiveness of the formation of communicative competence is achieved through the development of communicative listening skills. Improving the quality of students' knowledge is achieved through the use of a scientifically-based system of communication exercises, which includes exercises to overcome phonetic difficulties and difficulties in anticipation. Compliance with the formation of communicative competence contributes to the achievement of positive results in the learning process. For the formation of communicative competence in the process of learning a foreign language, it is necessary to develop a system of exercises that, given the difficulties in learning, will ensure their overcoming and lead to the achievement of the goal.

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